

Review

Challenges, risks and costs of food sharing. Insights from a systematic literature review

Vera Sadovska ^{*}

Lund University, The International Institute for Industrial Environmental Economics (IIIEE), Box 196, 22100, Lund, Sweden

HIGHLIGHTS

- Food sharing initiatives (FSIs) bring sustainable innovation to urban food systems
- An in-depth understanding of factors hindering FSIs' development is absent
- This research employs a systematic literature review of 52 articles on food sharing
- It categorises the challenges, risks, and costs of establishing and maintaining FSIs
- It proposes nine strategies and investment needs for FSIs' operation and development

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ABSTRACT

Current food systems are unsustainable, exacerbating environmental and socio-economic challenges. With 80 % of food consumed in cities, transforming urban food systems is vital. Urban food sharing initiatives (FSIs), which involve collective acts of growing, cooking, eating, and redistributing food, offer a promising alternative in sustainable urban transformations. However, FSIs often struggle to develop and scale. Academic literature has not adequately examined the factors hindering FSIs' establishment, operation, and scaling up. This study fills this gap through a systematic literature review of 55 articles, providing a comprehensive analysis of the challenges, risks, and costs faced by FSIs. It identifies six categories of challenges and risks each, as well as seven categories of costs. The study proposes nine mitigation strategies to address these issues and emphasises the need for a more detailed breakdown of costs and investments across different phases of FSI development. Additionally, it highlights the importance of support from governments, policymakers, health authorities, retailers, and charity organisations. The transformative potential of FSIs in addressing inefficiencies in current food systems is also underscored, alongside the need for a deeper understanding of the multi-dimensional challenges they face. The findings are particularly valuable for urban FSIs seeking to develop their practices, build capacity, and contribute to more resilient and sustainable urban food systems.

1. Introduction

Current food systems are unsustainable (Schneider, 2013; UNICEF, 2023). They contribute to greenhouse gas emissions, land degradation, waste, and health risks (Fardet and Rock, 2020; McClintock, 2014). Inequitable food distribution exacerbates poverty and hunger (United Nations, 2019). With over 30 % of produced food being wasted or lost annually (Qiu et al., 2024), achieving Sustainable Development Goals like poverty alleviation, zero hunger, and reduced inequalities demands urgent, fundamental changes in food systems. Transforming urban food systems towards sustainability is particularly critical (Serraj and Pingali,

2018; Zou et al., 2023), since 80 % of all food is consumed in cities (EAT, 2022). Food systems, encompassing production, processing, distribution, consumption, and waste management, involve a complex network of sectors, actors, and organisations.

The need to address unsustainable consumption and production was recognised as early as 1992 in 'Agenda 21' at the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development in Rio de Janeiro (UNCED, 1992). Food, along with housing, personal mobility, household goods, clothing, and footwear services, is one of the main domains contributing to the consumption footprint (EEA, 2024). Reducing its footprint through more sustainable consumption requires the involvement of a broad range of societal actors and crossing disciplinary boundaries to

^{*} Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: vera.sadovska@iiiee.lu.se (V. Sadovska), yuliya.voytenko_palgan@iiiee.lu.se (Y. Voytenko Palgan), oksana.mont@iiiee.lu.se (O. Mont).

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Abbreviations:

CSP -	Collaborative Supply Programme
FSI -	Food sharing initiative
PPI -	Platform Protection Insurance

devise and test “unconventional, dynamic, and adaptive solutions” (Mont, 2019, p. 2).

One such alternative system of provision is the sharing economy, which holds significant promise for promoting sustainability by optimizing resource use and reducing waste as it is viewed within the scholarly debate on sustainable consumption (Dabbous and Tarhini, 2021). Described as “an umbrella term for a wide variety of organisational models ... where goods, services, skills, and spaces are shared, exchanged, rented, or leased” (Mont et al., 2020, p. 2), the sharing economy experienced significant growth after the 2008 financial crisis, driven by advancements in digital technology. As sharing has long been a social convention, recent studies highlight the diversity of organisational forms and governance models shaping this domain (Guyader et al., 2023).

Early research on the sharing economy focused on defining the phenomenon (e.g., Curtis and Lehner, 2019; Frenken and Schor, 2017; Hamari et al., 2016). This was followed by a significant body of work on shared accommodation (e.g., Gyimóthy et al., 2020; Voytenko Palgan et al., 2017) and mobility (e.g., Plepys and Arbelaez Velez, 2021; van Waes et al., 2018). Research on the sharing economy has largely been dominated by analyses of two global multinational platforms—Airbnb for home sharing (Negi and Tripathi, 2023) and Uber for ride-hailing (Luo et al., 2021). Less attention has been given to non-commercial grassroots forms of sharing (Hult and Bradley, 2017; Sharp, 2018) that often share household goods such as tools and toys (Voytenko Palgan et al., 2021) or food (Davies et al., 2017a).

Food sharing emerged as a significant topic in sustainable consumption and sharing economy research, largely due to the contributions of McLaren and Agyeman (2015) and Davies et al. (2017a, 2017b). Their work established food sharing as a distinct niche within these literatures and situated it in the urban context. Food sharing is defined as “collective acts around food across the food system, including cooking and eating together, growing or composting together, redistributing surplus food, sharing food spaces, tools, knowledge, and seeds” (Voytenko Palgan and Sadovska, 2023, p. 10).¹ Since then, food sharing has been explored across various geographies, with studies examining over 4000 food-sharing initiatives (FSIs) in more than 100 cities across six continents (Davies et al., 2017a, 2017b). In-depth case studies have been conducted in cities across Germany (Braun et al., 2018; Morrow, 2019a), the UK (Marovelli, 2019), Ireland (Davies et al., 2019), Singapore (Rut and Davies, 2018), Australia (Booth and Whelan, 2014) and the US (Loh and Agyeman, 2019; Weymes and Davies, 2019), among others. FSIs are diverse organisations, having unique characteristics and goals. FSIs include producing food together through community-supported agriculture, gleaning or urban gardening; processing and preparing food collectively in cooking cooperatives or community kitchens; consuming food together in social canteens or home restaurants; and distributing and sharing food via community fridges, communal meals, or redistribution schemes that rescue surplus or donated food before it becomes waste (Edwards et al., 2023; Mackenzie and Davies, 2019; Miralles et al., 2017; Sarti et al., 2017). In this

¹ This definition is used by the project CULTIVATE: Co-designing food sharing innovation for resilience, which received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme (GA No 101083377). It is inspired by the definition in Davies et al. (2019).

way, FSIs encompass diverse ways of producing, processing and sharing food and meals that emphasise collaboration, solidarity and waste reduction.

The food sharing research has focused on conceptualising food sharing (Bachnik and Szumniak-Samolej, 2018; Davies and Evans, 2019); exploring different ontologies of food, i.e. how food is maintained, valued and moved within the sharing networks (Marovelli, 2019; Zapata Campos et al., 2026); the role of technology and digital tools in enabling or constraining food sharing (Midgley, 2019; Weymes and Davies, 2019); user perspectives on food sharing (Bosisio et al., 2024; Wiśniewska and Czernyszewicz, 2022); and sustainability of food sharing (Mackenzie and Davies, 2022; Michelini et al., 2020), discussing its potential for food waste reduction (Reynolds et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2025), enhanced justice (Herrero and Moragues-Faus, 2024), empowerment (Datta, 2019) and food poverty alleviation (Booth and Whelan, 2014). Economically, sharing makes food more affordable for individuals and local communities (Morrow, 2019a; Yamabe-Ledoux et al., 2023). It also allows including marginalised groups into the job market (Hennchen and Pregernig, 2020). Socially, FSIs build social bonds, mitigate asymmetrical relationships in communities (Marovelli, 2019), promote solidarity (D’Ambrosi, 2018), help the disadvantaged and improve public health through food education (Hennchen and Pregernig, 2020). Environmentally, FSIs lead to resource efficiency, reduction of greenhouse gas emissions (Yamabe-Ledoux et al., 2023) and effective waste management (Mazzucchelli et al., 2021).

While FSIs may bring sustainable change to local contexts, they are often small and operate in a specific area, which makes them dependent on local resources and constrained by contextual cultural norms (Davies et al., 2025). They work on the margins of the mainstream paradigm and cannot fully realise their sustainability potential. The highly contextual and local nature of FSIs presents challenges in scaling their impact and effecting broader systemic change (Marradi and Mulder, 2022). At the same time, transforming urban food systems towards sustainability can be significantly advanced by making them more widely accessible in cities. Therefore, a solid understanding of the factors influencing the establishment, operation, and scaling of FSIs offers a promising path forward. Scaling involves starting up a new FSI, employing an FSI across communities or replicating it in different contexts (Moore et al., 2015).

Emerging research on governance and scaling of FSIs highlights the challenges non-commercial FSIs face in growing (Loh and Agyeman, 2019; Morrow, 2019a), transforming or reinforcing socio-technical regimes (Rut and Davies, 2018) and navigating “processes of neoliberalization, privatization, gentrification, and enclosure” (Davies and Evans, 2019, p. 157). However, since there is no single solution for the development and scaling of innovations (Concilio et al., 2019; Verganti, 2008), creating favourable conditions for establishing, operating, and scaling FSIs requires understanding the factors that hinder these processes. The literature has failed to provide an in-depth understanding of such factors (Cangiano et al., 2017; Marradi and Mulder, 2022).

Although the sustainability potential and impact assessment of FSIs are increasingly being addressed in the literature (Datta, 2019; Davies et al., 2017a; Devillers, 2023; Hennig, 2019; Lim et al., 2017; Mackenzie and Davies, 2019, 2022; Michelini et al., 2020), and the appreciation of food sharing is growing, current knowledge about the organisation and functioning of FSIs in urban contexts remains fragmented and unsystematic (Kang et al., 2022; Mackenzie and Davies, 2019). While a few studies discuss the internal governance of FSIs, including their internal politics and organisational rules that determine everyday practices (Hennchen and Pregernig, 2020; Morrow, 2019a), there is a clear need to identify and systematically analyse the factors hindering the development and scaling of FSIs.

To address this gap, this article aims to provide a systematic understanding of the challenges, risks, and costs involved in establishing, maintaining and scaling FSIs in urban contexts. In doing so, it seeks to contribute to the sharing economy literature that engages with organisational research.

This research, grounded in a systematic literature review of 55 articles on food sharing, outlines its methodology in section 2 and results in section 3. It analyses the challenges, risks, and costs of establishing and maintaining FSIs, discussing the necessary investments for their operation in section 4, where a framework is also proposed. Section 5 concludes the paper, addressing its limitations and suggesting future research directions.

2. Method

2.1. Research approach

This article reviews a modest but rapidly growing body of literature on food sharing. The academic literature focuses on the positive impacts of food sharing and its benefits (e.g. Datta, 2019; Michelini et al., 2018; Tsuji et al., 2020). At the same time, discussing the establishment, operation and development of FSIs without understanding the other side of the picture is difficult. Therefore, this study has focused on collecting academic framings of the challenges, risks and costs of FSIs. For this purpose, a systematic literature review was conducted, which is a standard method in research on social innovation and food sharing research (Jin et al., 2018; Sánchez-Vergara et al., 2021; Schanes and Stagl, 2019).

A systematic literature review was chosen for several reasons. Although food sharing practices are included in sharing economy studies (e.g. Puram and Gurumurthy, 2023), a systematic approach focusing particularly on FSIs has not been used before. Furthermore, the literature in this area spans a range of disciplines and topics, such as urban geography, sharing economy, social innovation, and food commons, making systematic literature reviews particularly relevant (Williams et al., 2021). In addition, systematic literature reviews can inform practical solutions by providing a reliable analysis of studies from different disciplines (Briner and Denyer, 2012). Finally, a systematic literature review, an objective method with explicit inclusion/exclusion criteria and a transparent selection process, ensures rigorous results and limits bias (Cook et al., 1997; Davis et al., 1995). To the best of our knowledge, this is the first systematic literature review synthesising and categorising the factors hindering the establishment and maintenance of FSIs.

2.2. Data collection

The Scopus database was used for the source search, as it is one of the largest databases of scientific articles with a wide coverage of disciplines and different navigation options (Carrera-Rivera et al., 2022; Ginieis et al., 2012). Fig. 1 shows the flowchart based on PRISMA guidelines (Liberati et al., 2009) with the steps of the selection process.

1. Identification step

Step 1 in the systematic literature review includes the identification of keywords, the combinations of which are then used to generate search strings. Since it is recommended that the keywords are selected and agreed upon in collaboration with several researchers (Tranfield et al., 2003), all co-authors and a lead academic expert² in the field of urban food sharing were involved in this process. It was decided to use several combinations of words (Fig. 2) with 'food sharing' as the base and different aspects (e.g. costs, challenges, drivers) as additional words. The

² Prof. Anna Davies supported scoping of the literature search for this article. In her academic work, she contributed significantly to establishing and developing the urban food sharing field by leading two large European projects SHARECITY (GA#646883; <https://sharecity.ie/>) and CULTIVATE (GA#101083377; <https://cultivate-project.eu/>), and having published extensively on the topic (c.f., Davies et al. (2017a, 2017b).

concept of food commons was also included, as this terminology is used in related fields. In total, 14 keyword combinations were applied. The database was searched in September 2023 and yielded 538 results, further filtered according to the PRISMA guidelines (Liberati et al., 2009).

2. Screening step

In Step 2, the search results were screened for publication type, study design, and language (Table 1). Only international peer-reviewed journal articles in English, the most common academic language (Bocanegra-Valle, 2014), were included to allow for the quality control of the studies. Only original empirical studies were included to attend to primary sources of information, while review and conceptual articles were excluded (Cook et al., 1997). These criteria resulted in the exclusion of 112 articles from the initial search. Due to using 14 different search strings, 88 duplicate articles were excluded in the next step.

3. Eligibility identification step

In Step 3, the set of 338 unique records was assessed based on their titles and abstracts. This was done to check the article's relevance to the topic of FSIs. Food sharing in the sense of collective acts around food and food-related objects (e.g., tools, seeds), spaces, skills, and knowledge that take place across the food system, from growing and composting to cooking and eating to redistributing surplus food together (Davies and Legg, 2018; Voytenko Palgan and Sadovska, 2023), was taken as a prerequisite for inclusion in the full-text screening step (Table 1).

However, as this study focuses on FSIs as organisations, programmes or structures, this view was used to select eligible articles. This screening resulted in the exclusion of 283 articles, and the selection of 55 articles for the full-text analysis.

4. Inclusion step

Step 4 implied a full-text analysis of 55 articles to assess their relevance to the scope of the study. Namely, articles that contained information on the challenges, risks, and costs of FSIs were included in the review. Those excluded at this stage had less relevance to the urban context and FSIs (e.g., articles about food sharing inside a family). This led to the further exclusion of 12 sources. This pool of literature was extended with the help of the snowballing technique, meaning that the reference lists of the initial articles were checked. After completing all the steps, the final list of articles comprised 52 items.

To ensure a more comprehensive coverage of the literature, the Web of Science Core Collection database was additionally searched using the same 14 keyword combinations (Fig. 2) and timeframe (publications up to September 2023) as applied in Scopus. This search yielded 603 initial records. After filtering for publication type ("article") and language (English), the results were reduced to 427 items. These 427 records were compared to the 338 unique records from Scopus, resulting in 89 additional unique records. The 89 records were then screened based on titles and abstracts for relevance to FSIs in urban contexts, following the same eligibility criteria (Table 1). This led to the inclusion of 3 additional articles in the review, complementing the 52 items obtained from Scopus and snowballing, for a final total of 55 articles.

2.3. Data analysis

The full texts of the 55 articles were analysed and categorised into three levels of codes using NVivo 12 qualitative analysis software. The first-level codes, deduced from the research aim outlined in the Introduction, were the categories of "challenges," "risks," and "costs." For each of these first-level codes, one researcher inductively developed third-level codes using examples and quotes from the reviewed literature, documenting them in a data sheet. Intercoder reliability was then

Fig. 1. PRISMA flowchart of the systematic literature review process.

DATABASE	SEARCH REQUEST	NO. OF RECORDS
SCOPUS	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("food sharing" AND cost*)	123
	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("food sharing" AND driver*)	14
	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("food sharing" AND impact*)	83
	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("food sharing" AND challenge*)	74
	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("food sharing" AND governance)	11
	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("food sharing" AND sustainability)	42
	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("food sharing" AND urban)	54
	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("food sharing" AND local)	68
	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("food sharing" AND "business model*")	8
	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("food sharing" AND (city OR cities))	40
	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("food sharing initiativ*")	13
	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("food sharing landscape")	1
	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("food commons" AND sharing)	6
	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("food commons" AND "cost-benefit analysis")	1

Fig. 2. The search keyword.

Table 1 Eligibility criteria.

Category	Inclusion criteria
Topics	Articles containing information on challenges, risks, and costs of FSIs Articles with a major focus on food sharing organisations, programmes, and initiatives as units of analysis Urban context
Study design	Empirical studies (qualitative and quantitative)
Publication status	Peer-reviewed journal articles published until September 2023
Language	Articles published in English

tested during a workshop among the three co-authors who 1) discussed and revised the third-level codes, and 2) inductively grouped the third-level codes into second-level categories.

The reviewed articles exhibit a diverse geographical distribution. The United Kingdom emerges as the most frequently studied context, appearing in 13 articles. Germany follows with six articles, emphasizing case studies in cities like Berlin and southern regions. Five articles adopt a global perspective, analysing food sharing across multiple continents or large-scale datasets involving hundreds of cities. Ireland and the Netherlands each feature in five articles. Similarly, five articles address broader European contexts or comparative analyses. India, Italy, Japan, and the United States are each covered in 3 articles, incorporating

themes like behavioural interventions in India and urban solidarity economies in the US. The rest of the articles feature Australia, Canada, Austria, Bangladesh, China, Eswatini, New Zealand, Poland, and Spain. Four articles do not specify a particular geographical location, focusing instead on general conceptual frameworks or experimental models.

The categorisations of challenges, risks, and costs were combined into three frameworks and visualised as sunburst diagrams with inner circles of each diagram presenting the second-level codes and the outer circles presenting the third-level codes (see Figs. 3–5). Following the analysis of each second-level code, presented in section 3, a comparative analysis was conducted to inductively identify nine common themes across the second-level codes for challenges, risks, and costs. These themes include laws and regulations, resources, operations, management, safety and health, justice and inclusivity, rebound effects, trust and image, and network management processes. Based on these common themes, mitigation strategies to address the risks and challenges of FSIs were proposed (section 4.1). A similar approach was used to identify investment needs for the costs of FSIs (section 4.2).

3. Results and analysis

The literature shows a variety of organisational forms, sizes and business models of FSIs, used to adapt to different goals and conditions. Volunteer-based surplus food redistribution initiatives, digitally enabled food sharing platforms, gifting of food or skills to reduce food waste, community kitchens and gardens are just a few examples of the types of FSIs. Market transactions do not dominate the food sharing landscape, with many transactions being of a gifting nature. There exist for-profit organisations that offer food-sharing opportunities for money through mobile applications. However, the success of these applications is challenging due to the need for high levels of participation and positive user experience. The motivational aspect of FSIs is their willingness to address environmental and social issues of food security, waste reduction and community building.

The following sub-sections present an analysis of 55 academic articles to identify the challenges, risks, and costs of establishing and maintaining FSIs. The results for the second and third level categories of challenges, risks and costs are presented in sections 3.1–3.3 and summarised in Figs. 3–5 respectively.

3.1. Challenges

The challenges FSIs face during their establishment and maintenance can be organised into six categories: organisational management, resources, user participation, network management, image, and regulations (Fig. 3).

3.1.1. Organisational management

In the early stages of establishing FSIs, a significant drop-off in participation among those involved in FSIs is typical. This requires the adaptation of FSIs' **operational scale** to their participants' limited capacity and time (Berns et al., 2023). While the lack of strict instructions seeks to encourage participation, in reality it makes it more difficult for those interested to become involved (Edwards et al., 2023). The lack of precise routines and guidelines leaves potential contributors unsure how to navigate the community and contribute effectively.

Regarding **internal governance**, it is challenging for FSIs to maintain a non-hierarchical model and fair power distribution, which reflect the dynamic nature of participation in a community-based organisation (Morrow, 2019a). Berns et al. (2023) report that the informal development of hierarchical leadership in an FSI led to stress among its participants because none of them actively chose leadership roles. Further, undefined roles and a lack of clear labour division among FSI participants create barriers to their participation. Addressing internal governance challenges requires effective communication and flexible decision-making that can accommodate the complexities of fluctuating

participation in FSIs.

3.1.2. Resources

To ensure their operations, FSIs rely on financial and non-financial resources. As such, the lack of **financial viability** is recognised "as a common barrier for most food sharing services" (Yamabe-Ledoux et al., 2023, p. 15) when even FSIs with for-profit sharing models struggle to become profitable. In most cases, FSIs depend on external funding from philanthropy, private and public sectors (Loh and Agyeman, 2019).

Non-financial resources essential for establishing and maintaining FSIs include access to capital assets, surplus food, knowledge, skills and human capacity, all of which can be challenging. Due to the restricted budgets of FSIs, their access to **capital assets** like equipment, new technologies, or innovative software is limited, which is why FSIs "often adopt existing technologies and social media to organise their work" (Berns et al., 2023, 986).

FSIs depend on food donors and retailers to ensure **food supply**. FSIs need to secure efficient and timely food provision to their users, for example, by creating and managing a larger pool of suppliers (Yamabe-Ledoux et al., 2023). For food donors, often retail chains, participation in food sharing implies disclosure of the surplus food they produce, which "could be seen as a sign of inefficiency and compromise their reputation" (Yamabe-Ledoux et al., 2023, p. 15).

On the distribution side, FSIs are challenged by the limited **human capacity** due to the lack of personnel (Berns et al., 2023) and quick staff turnover (Yamabe-Ledoux et al., 2023). Grassroots FSIs often face hurdles in recruiting volunteers to perform tasks for the organization, drawing lessons from similar initiatives to configure participation and decision-making processes (Berns et al., 2023).

Furthermore, there is a general lack of **knowledge and skills** about food waste reduction (Davison et al., 2022) and surplus food redistribution, both of which are recognised as "[t]he most significant obstacles" (Yamabe-Ledoux et al., 2023, 15). In garden contexts, gardeners express interest in organized surplus distribution but encounter lack of knowledge in aligning charitable goals with practical implementation, particularly for disadvantaged groups (Schäfer et al., 2023).

3.1.3. User participation

Regarding user participation, FSIs are challenged by the need to ensure active, continuous and inclusive user involvement.

The lack of **active user participation** is reported as a significant challenge in the literature (Hennchen and Pregernig, 2020). It is influenced by factors specific to different types of food sharing. For urban gardening, there are physical constraints, such as small residential plots and limited space for cultivation. There are also institutional barriers, for example, the illegality of urban gardening in some areas (Tevera and Simelane, 2014). For digital food sharing platforms there is a mismatch between the number of subscribers and active users, with a small share of committed users remaining regularly active (Yamabe-Ledoux et al., 2023).

The lack of **inclusive user participation** can arise when, for instance, digital sharing platforms cater mainly to those who are digitally literate (Davies et al., 2017a), while participation in urban gardening is open to people with a significant amount of free time to maintain growing activities (Hennchen and Pregernig, 2020).

3.1.4. Image

FSIs face challenges in establishing and maintaining a reliable image such as nurturing public acceptance and trust, appealing to varied cultural preferences and facilitating behavioural change.

There may be prejudice against the consumption of surplus food and a lack of public awareness about food waste, further hampering redistribution efforts. Food sharing practices such as urban gardening and meal sharing face significant challenges regarding **public acceptance and trust**. Scepticism often undermines urban gardening initiatives, with outsiders questioning the motives behind these community efforts

Fig. 3. Categories of challenges for food sharing initiatives.

(Hennchen and Pregernig, 2020). Similarly, meal sharing has had strong adverse reactions due to perceived health and safety risks (Zurek, 2016). Lack of trust is a reported challenge among the users of digital food sharing platforms (Berns et al., 2023). These concerns are linked to **cultural preferences** in food consumption (Makov et al., 2023). For example, in some societies, cultural norms may lead to reluctance to consume food beyond its expiration date.

Another aspect of food sharing image is translating awareness into **behaviour change**. Studies have shown that even when people have a positive attitude towards food sharing, it does not necessarily translate into them using food sharing services. While "Foodsavers" believe that providing individuals with the correct information will lead to behaviour change and waste reduction, this assumption may be overly optimistic (Schanes and Stagl, 2019). It overstates the power of awareness and information, overrates individual agency, and overlooks the structural and systemic factors contributing to food waste. Therefore, while awareness is a crucial first step, it does not guarantee behavioural change, underscoring the complexity of achieving sustainable change.

3.1.5. Network management

FSIs operate in a complex landscape where their existence, operation and financial viability depend on **agency and power** distribution within the network of actors from policy, industry, community and civil society. As such, authorities at different levels define regulatory and policy regimes in which FSIs operate while public, private and philanthropy actors provide financial and non-financial resources to FSIs as discussed above (Loh and Agyeman, 2019). In addition to dependence on some influential actors, FSIs engaged in cooking, eating and redistributing surplus food rely on food donors, who can withdraw their supply of products due to changing circumstances (Berns et al., 2023).

Inter-organisational conflicts and contestations are common in relationships where power is unequally distributed, as different

stakeholders may have different views on how FSIs should operate. Conflicts may arise over the allocation of resources, which is particularly challenging for FSIs with scarce resources and high competition for the same resources (Braun et al., 2018). Negotiating fairness in surplus distribution models presents ongoing challenges, as seen in Swedish grassroots initiatives, where volunteers must balance equitable access with practical logistics (Berns et al., 2023)

Competition with other food producers is an essential challenge for FSIs. Studies show that in some cases both sides have negative opinions about each other. From the conventional business side, the practice of food sharing "raises strong negative reactions, not the least among the restaurateurs and chefs, who see it as a threat to their businesses, unfair cheap competition and a potential source of bad press" (Zurek, 2016, p. 680). From the food sharing side, the scale of many FSIs does not allow them to produce the cheapest product, creating a situation where, for example, "they are competing with less expensive conventionally produced sauce supplied by large distributors and struggling to develop a viable business model for this farm-to-institution product" (Loh and Agyeman, 2019, p. 213).

3.1.6. Regulations

Navigating the regulatory landscape to operate effectively and safely is a concern for all FSIs. Although the social practice of food sharing is not new, FSIs find themselves in a space where there is no **legal definition of food**, meaning that "drawing the line between 'food' and 'non-food' is a key challenge both for the actors involved in urban food sharing initiatives and for social scientists" (Davies and Evans, 2019, p. 157).

This challenge is exacerbated by conservative and **restrictive regulations** that create barriers to community-based sharing. For example, consumer protection regulations view urban refrigerators as a source of risk, with no one held accountable for the consequences (Morrow,

Fig. 4. Categories of risks for food sharing initiatives.

2019a). Legal frameworks pose significant obstacles to economical distribution of garden products, limiting gardeners' ability to formalize sharing beyond personal use (Schäfer et al., 2023). Similar regulatory constraints in Japan hinder the scaling of business incentives for food sharing, requiring adaptations to comply with food safety and distribution laws (Igeta and Nakamura, 2022)

Digital food sharing platforms, where the distinction between seller and buyer is blurred, suffer from regulations designed for traditional businesses (Yamabe-Ledoux et al., 2023). Specifically for urban gardening, *land rights* that enable "gaining long-term affordable access to land" (Loh and Agyeman, 2019, p. 218) constitute a critical regulatory challenge.

3.2. Risks

The risks faced by FSIs during their start-up phase and operations have been organised into six categories: health and safety, justice and inclusivity, rebound effects, operational risks, trust, and regulatory uncertainty (Fig. 4).

3.2.1. Health and safety

Food sharing can present significant health and safety risks. From the **public health** perspective, sharing unmarketable products or leftovers is considered the most high-risk form of food sharing. Public fridges, for example, have been criticised as being unhygienic and threatening individual and public health (Zurek, 2016). Food unfit for human consumption can be a cause of foodborne diseases. The Food Standards Agency (FSA) has expressed concerns about its ability to respond effectively to food safety crises in public fridges (Morrow, 2019a). The informality of food sharing often means that it occurs outside of the complex regulatory systems governing food safety, from production and processing to handling and transport. This lack of oversight can result in food reaching consumers without the necessary health and safety checks, posing a risk to **consumer wellbeing**. Moreover, certain food ingredients can be a source of allergic reactions, which can be dangerous to consumers suffering from allergies or intolerances (Zurek, 2016).

3.2.2. Justice and inclusivity

There are several risks associated with justice and inclusivity of food sharing. The way FSIs organise their work can sometimes lead to **social exclusion**. For instance, local food produce from urban gardens may

Fig. 5. Categories of costs for food sharing initiatives.

only be accessible to relatively wealthy and mobile customers (Braun et al., 2018), while digital sharing platforms require access to technology and social networks "that those most in need of food assistance" may not have (Makov et al., 2020, p. 5).

As essential as they are, food banks face criticism for prioritising self-sustenance and own expansion instead of improving food system efficiency (Booth and Whelan, 2014). While food donations reduce costs for the industry for discharging, transportation and administration of the food surplus (e.g., tax reductions for donations, avoiding high fees for dumping food waste in landfill sites), this leads to the proliferation and **corporatisation of food banks** as they serve to support food industry, but not addressing food insecurity or equity of people in need (*ibid.*). This is a sign of social policy failure leading to unmet food obligations.

Moreover, despite their diversity, existing food sharing practices may **perpetuate inequalities** between donors and recipients. In the design of certain mobile food sharing applications, it is visible who is donating more or receiving more; thus, people may feel the same stigma reported by the users of food banks when using these applications (Harvey et al., 2020), potentially deterring participation in these activities. Research shows that applying data modeling to socio-economic factors within food sharing networks, such as OLIO, can uncover hidden patterns of deprivation. Ignoring these insights may lead to undetected poverty and limit the effectiveness of food sharing initiatives (Nica-Avram et al., 2021).

3.2.3. Rebound effects³

While redistributing near-expiration products from supermarkets,

³ The rebound effect refers to the phenomenon where improvements in energy or resource efficiency lead to a less-than-expected reduction in overall consumption due to behavioral or economic responses. This effect manifests as increased demand, behavioral adjustments or economic growth.

food sharing platforms may inadvertently discourage waste reduction at the source and indirectly encourage retailer **wasteful practices** (Mackenzie and Davies, 2019). Additionally, although these platforms offer economic benefits for businesses, they could limit opportunities for food banks and social services to aid the disadvantaged (Booth and Whelan, 2014).

Using discarded food from commercial sources to address food poverty may, over time, **entrench food poverty** rather than resolve it, as it often stems from broader systemic problems (Mackenzie and Davies, 2019).

In the digital context, sharing platforms can increase societal benefits by allowing food banks to operate on a larger scale. However, as some food sharing platforms incorporate market-based elements, this can limit the development of models that promote social welfare by encouraging the **commodification of food** (Michellini et al., 2018), meaning transformation of shared food into a marketable commodity, and by this, limiting the social function of food sharing. This dichotomy underscores the need for a balanced approach that considers economic viability and social impact in the design and operation of food sharing platforms.

3.2.4. Operational risks

The primary operational risks in food sharing relate to food handling, storing, and distributing. Fresh food products have minimal risks associated with processing and preparing food. However, storing and transporting could **damage food** and impact its suitability for consumption (Zurek, 2016). Even with efficient food waste prevention programmes in place, there may be challenges in delivering surplus food in time. This could lead to food waste, defeating the primary purpose of FSLs. Organisations like Open Table adopted procedures to mitigate some of these risks to provide healthy and nutritious meals using fresh, mainly vegan food to lower the risk of food contamination (Edwards,

2021).

3.2.5. Trust

Trust is of utmost importance in food sharing, but it can be easily eroded due to different factors. Uncertainties about food storage and safety significantly affect trust in food sharing (Morone et al., 2018). The shift from local, community-based sharing to online platforms introduces another change in trust dynamics. Local communities often have familiarity with food processing and hygiene, but this assurance diminishes when sharing extends to strangers online (Veen, 2019). The absence of this familiarity not only affects trust but also influences the willingness to accept risks. Users of online food sharing platforms face increased **transaction uncertainty** due to dealing with unbranded individual sellers, which casts doubt on product credibility. Additionally, since these platforms typically do not produce the food, they have limited control over quality and consistency, exacerbating the uncertainty (Luo et al., 2021).

3.2.6. Regulatory uncertainty

Regulatory risks in food sharing mainly stem from the ambiguity in applying existing laws to sharing activities. The lack of specific regulations for sharing business models creates a risk of future legal challenges, as current regulatory grey areas might be used to bypass rules intended to protect the public interest. This uncertainty can **deter investment** in sharing businesses, especially those operating across borders, which could impede the development of the sharing economy (Zurek, 2016).

Without a holistic urban food policy, food is governed as a commercial commodity (Davies et al., 2019). The literature shows that rules relating to food sharing may be retained, adapted by agencies mainly applying the precautionary principle, "which relies on a negative definition of 'unsafety'", while the prevention of food hazards is given secondary role (Morrow, 2019a, p. 204). In Japan, strict legal frameworks pose a risk of non-compliance for food sharing, such as digital coupon systems, highlighting the need for supportive policies to ease regulatory barriers and support digital implementation (Igeta and Nakamura, 2022). This risk-based policy understanding exemplifies an evolving and **uncertain regulatory landscape** for food sharing.

Eliminating a clear physical intermediary, e.g. point of sale, in food sharing networks redistributes risks from the central provider to donors and recipients. This **blurring of boundaries** between personal and professional provision of commercial services can lead to increased risks for all parties involved (Harvey et al., 2020). Simultaneously, legislative and controlling bodies face the **inability to enforce** existing rules developed for traditional business models to new sharing modes of economic activity (Davies et al., 2019). This requires the development of new guidelines and regulations that can effectively govern food sharing activities.

3.3. Costs

Costs that FSIs encounter can be divided into several categories, including operational costs, administrative costs, assets, personnel costs, communication and outreach costs, public relations and image, and legal compliance costs (Fig. 5).

3.3.1. Operational costs

Operational costs of FSIs encompass expenses related to their maintenance. For FSIs engaged in cooking, eating and redistributing surplus food, there are always costs associated with **food sourcing**. FSIs must find a reliable source of food supplies in sufficient quantities, which entails personnel costs and time for networking. Sometimes, food banks directly purchase food from manufacturers and participate in the Collaborative Supply Programme (CSP) (Booth and Whelan, 2014). The CSP, an initiative of the food bank industry, aims to secure stable supplies of essential food items like milk, cereal, and pasta at a significantly reduced cost (Booth and Whelan, 2014). When there is a shortage of

donated ingredients, food banks collaborate with government and corporate donors to meet production needs (Booth and Whelan, 2014).

Transportation and logistics costs are also significant. FSIs organise food delivery, sorting and storage experiencing logistics costs and requiring time of volunteers and eventual staff. To offset transport and storage expenses, FSI's organisational clients sometimes contribute a nominal handling fee per kilogramme of food (Booth and Whelan, 2014).

3.3.2. Administrative costs

The **utilities and space rental costs** vary based on the lease type and location. Marovelli (2019) provides examples of FSIs operating in temporary spaces, such as within the King's Cross redevelopment site under a 'meanwhile lease' or in spaces owned by other organisations, e.g., charities. Some FSIs secure long-term rent agreements with city councils.

Office supplies and subscriptions are a minor part of administrative costs. The most significant expenditure remains aiding members of the FSI community and related **management and paperwork**.

3.3.3. Asset costs

FSIs rely heavily on Information and Communication Technology tools and social media for outreach and engagement. Machine learning analysis of sharing networks incurs data processing costs but enables better quantification of deprivation-related expenses in FSIs (Nica-Avram et al., 2021). **Technology and software** are, therefore, pivotal for connecting with users, policymakers, and organisations, as well as for raising awareness, communicating with the public, and celebrating achievements (Morrow, 2019b).

Premise **maintenance** is another crucial expense for FSIs. Edwards (2021) notes the importance of having premises with food safety certifications. This is especially critical for eating and cooking FSIs that prioritise serving healthy and nutritious meals, thereby challenging the perception of food sharing as "second class food for second class people" (Schneider, 2013, p. 761).

Equipment costs are a significant concern, particularly for FSIs lacking a permanent space or having limited funds. Marovelli (2019) discusses the constraints faced by FSIs that operate in spaces like local churches or supper club venues. The inability to invest in professional kitchen equipment, especially for handling and storing sensitive items like meat or fish, is challenging. Furthermore, Hennchen and Pregernig (2020) highlight the financial requirements for maintaining the existing infrastructure, garden aesthetics and procuring necessary landscaping tools. These expenses are integral to the functioning of FSIs, particularly those involved in community gardening and similar projects.

In addition, **asset depreciation** is a continual expense for FSIs owning equipment, from trucks and forklifts to computers.

3.3.4. Personnel costs

Volunteer time constitutes a significant component of unpaid personnel costs. Berns et al. (2023) observe that voluntary efforts in FSIs frequently occur under conditions of scarce resources, including human capital. Configuring capacities in grassroots initiatives, such as selecting digital tools for food sharing, entails costs related to volunteer time and adaptation from previously learned experiences (Berns et al., 2023). Hennchen and Pregernig (2020) add that while FSIs are inclusive and encourage active participation, they also require a significant time commitment and long-term involvement from their members. Paid and unpaid community organisers are critical in creating online and offline community infrastructure and running operations smoothly. Such contributions go beyond what is typically showcased on digital platforms, signifying a substantial investment in human resources (Morrow, 2019b). Morrow (2019a) highlights that some FSIs manage to allocate funds to pay **salaries** to the most skilled staff.

Staff training is a crucial personnel cost. The earlier discussed inability of cooking and eating FSIs with restricted budgets to invest in

professional equipment for handling sensitive food underscores the need for proper personnel training in food safety to prevent cross-contamination (Marovelli, 2019). This is particularly important when involving volunteers or trainees in cooking sessions. Moreover, managing community resources, i.e. food, fridges, knowledge and skills, requires ongoing training and skill development (Morrow, 2019a).

3.3.5. Communication and outreach costs

FSIs engage in internal and external communication. While internal communication encompasses interactions among FSI personnel and data archiving, external communication and outreach are important for FSIs to remain visible and accountable to their users and other stakeholders. These include, for example, maintenance of a website, social media pages, a hotline, or a newsletter. All communication and outreach activities come at a cost, mainly linked to the time of personnel managing the communication channels. Communication and outreach costs of FSIs referred to in the literature include maintaining regular external communication channels (e.g., a hotline, a newsletter) and engaging with civic and legal processes.

Maintaining regular **communication channels** such as a hotline represents a notable expense and an essential component of offline social infrastructure dedicated to community land access support for organisations like 596 Acres and the Living Lots portal. This service, managed by staff members, was a crucial connection for individuals seeking guidance in organising property access (Morrow, 2019a). Similarly, publishing a newsletter, which is a comprehensive undertaking that extends beyond the basic collection and assembly of information, necessitates accurate and regular (often monthly) reporting (Morrow, 2019a).

Civic and **legal process engagement** at different levels, e.g., lobbying for policy changes, is time-consuming and costly. As such, Foodsharing.de collected over 25000 citizen signatures for a petition to the Berlin Senate, advocating for reclassifying their fridges as "private transfer locations" instead of businesses and supporting their case with health and safety arguments (Morrow, 2019a). Similarly, interaction with city agencies forms a significant part of communication expenses. This may involve maintaining a detailed record of all interactions, i.e., meeting notes, photographs, updates on progress in different processes, email correspondence, and legal documentation. This extensive digital record is essential for operational continuity if initial organisers no longer engage with the FSI (Morrow, 2019b).

3.3.6. Costs related to public relations and image

Building a reliable image is of utmost importance for FSIs. Trust and reputation are key elements in any transaction, especially when engaging with strangers (Veen, 2019). Digital FSIs often implement review and rating systems to foster trust, enhancing transparency and minimising user risks. Monitoring and addressing reviews is essential to uphold an FSI's credibility, though it requires a time investment. Trust and reputation are equally crucial in face-to-face interactions with FSIs.

Digitally enabled FSIs incur **insurance** costs if they decide to purchase Platform Protection Insurance (PPI). PPI is essential for establishing a reputation among consumers. This involves the initial insurance costs that the platform covers (ex-ante) and additional expenses for handling default incidents (ex-post) to safeguard consumer interests (Luo et al., 2021). This approach is distinct from typical product guarantee policies where platforms might only address post-incident costs. Notably, in business-to-consumer interactions, it is common for consumers to bear insurance costs. However, for platform-based FSIs, the responsibility for PPI costs often falls on the platform. This expenditure is significant since FSI platforms, acting as intermediaries, do not have direct control over product quality, thus necessitating a robust insurance strategy to maintain consumer trust and a positive image.

3.3.7. Costs related to legal compliance

As for **licensing and certification**, employing individuals with food safety certificates is a regulatory requirement that incurs costs for FSIs, particularly regarding staff training and certification processes (Edwards, 2021). Moreover, Davies et al. (2019) discuss the substantial paperwork involved in surplus food initiatives, particularly in signing off liability agreements. The fear of legal repercussions from food donors leads to considerable food waste, as donors are hesitant to distribute food that might not be used correctly. This legal apprehension necessitates a substantial amount of administrative work to ensure compliance and safety in food distribution. Allotment gardeners in Germany face administrative costs in navigating legal barriers to surplus distribution, though non-economic motivations like enjoyment reduce perceived financial burdens (Schäfer et al., 2023).

The **taxation** of sharing activities is a complex issue that presents financial implications for FSIs. Zurek (2016) points out the difficulty tax administrations face due to the variety of food sharing models and the differing scales of income generation. From cost recovery and symbolic contributions to actual remuneration, the taxation challenges are further compounded in cases of food bartering or contributions to a shared pool, where establishing a direct link between services and remuneration in kind for taxation purposes is challenging.

To signal product quality and reduce consumer risk, FSIs often implement **self-regulation** measures that involve costs. Luo et al. (2021) mention that cooking and eating platform-based FSIs may require sellers to obtain health certificates and adhere to specific dress codes, such as wearing a cooking uniform with a chef's hat and mouth-covering mask. Such measures, while enhancing safety and trust, add to the financial burden of FSIs.

Morrow (2019b) describes the extensive **engagement in legal processes** of FSI staff and members, who may represent community interests in court, which often extends over months and requires considerable resources. This includes the direct costs of legal representation, court preparation and attendance expenses, and the administrative burden of documenting these activities. Moreover, FSIs may engage in lobbying activities to change the regulations, as earlier described in the case of Foodsharing.de. This comes at the cost of time, effort and skills of FSI staff (Morrow, 2019a).

4. The way forward: addressing challenges, risks and costs of FSIs

This section compares the findings on the challenges, risks, and costs that FSIs face and identifies common themes across these areas. Through this comparative analysis of the themes, we develop a nuanced understanding of mitigation strategies FSIs can adopt to address the challenges and risks (sub-section 4.1), secure investments for FSIs' operations (sub-section 4.2), and discuss how different stakeholders can facilitate urban food sharing (sub-section 4.3). The mitigation strategies represent an interpretive analytical work informed by existing evidence, intended to guide practice and future research.

4.1. Mitigation strategies to address risks and challenges of FSIs

Consolidating findings and identifying the common themes resulted in nine potential strategies FSIs may develop to address identified challenges and mitigate risks. The subsequent phase of analysis focused on the identification of thematic commonalities between the challenges, risks, and costs, as well as their correlation with mitigation strategies (see Table 2).

To ensure consistency, existing **laws and regulations** need to be clarified and adapted in consultation with agencies handling food sharing activities. The blurred boundaries between personal and professional provisions in food sharing (Harvey et al., 2020; Yamabe-Ledoux et al., 2023) call for developing new guidelines and regulations, considering the redistribution of risks between providers and

Table 2
Recurring themes across challenges, risks and costs of FSIs and corresponding mitigation strategies.

Themes	Example challenges/risks/costs identified	Mitigation strategies (as proposed in literature)	Source examples
Laws and regulations	Regulatory uncertainty; restrictive or ambiguous regulations; liability and compliance costs	Clarify and adapt existing laws; develop new guidelines specific to FSIs; involve stakeholders in regulatory design; policy advocacy	Harvey et al. (2020); Yamabe-Ledoux et al. (2023); Loh and Agyeman (2019); Zurek (2016)
Resources	Lack of financial viability; limited assets and equipment; dependence on donors; personnel shortages	Diversify funding sources; develop sustainable business models; partnerships for resources; volunteer management and training	Loh and Agyeman (2019); Yamabe-Ledoux et al. (2023)
Operations	High operational costs; food handling and logistics risks; staff turnover	Invest in logistics planning and infrastructure (storage, vehicles); training on food handling and safety; adjust operational scale to capacity	Booth and Whelan (2014)
Management	Informal hierarchies; unclear roles; governance tensions	Provide clear guidelines for participation; define roles and responsibilities; foster inclusive and flexible decision-making	Berns et al. (2023); Morrow (2019b)
Safety and health	Food safety concerns; risk of foodborne illness; insurance costs	Establish hygiene protocols; training for staff and volunteers; invest in proper storage and transport; insurance solutions	Morrow (2019b); Zurek (2016)
Justice and inclusivity	Risk of exclusion (digital divide, socio-economic barriers); stigma of participation; inequitable access	Outreach to underprivileged groups; partnerships with municipalities and NGOs; digital literacy programs; reduce stigma through awareness campaigns	Hennchen and Pregernig (2020); Makov et al. (2020)
Rebound effects	Risk of entrenching food poverty; enabling wasteful retailer practices; commodification of food	Balance economic viability with social mission; educate users about responsible consumption; encourage retailers to reduce waste at source	Michellini et al. (2018); Wiśniewska and Czernyszewicz (2022)
Trust and image	Low public trust; negative perceptions of surplus food; cultural barriers	Transparency in operations; robust review and rating systems; culturally sensitive outreach; communication campaigns	Makov et al. (2020); Veen (2019)
Network management processes	Dependence on powerful actors; conflicts with other food producers; competition for resources	Build diverse partnerships; mechanisms for conflict resolution; fair resource allocation; open dialogue with stakeholders	Berns et al. (2023)

consumers. For FSIs, consistent regulations can mitigate uncertainty and stimulate investment (Loh and Agyeman, 2019; Zurek, 2016). Involving all stakeholders in developing these regulations can ensure they are comprehensive and uphold the public interest.

Many FSIs rely on external funding and **resources** and experience difficulties in becoming financially viable (Loh and Agyeman, 2019; Yamabe-Ledoux et al., 2023). To mitigate this, FSIs could explore diverse funding sources, develop sustainable business models, and advocate for stable policy support. Non-financial resources, such as access to assets, equipment, food for distribution, knowledge, skills, and human capacity, are also crucial. FSIs could seek partnerships or donations for necessary resources. FSIs also depend on food providers for food supply. By creating and managing a larger pool of providers, they can secure efficient and timely food provision (Yamabe-Ledoux et al., 2023). This could also involve educating food donors about the benefits and impacts of food sharing to overcome concerns about the inefficiency of food redistribution. The challenge of limited personnel and quick staff turnover (Yamabe-Ledoux et al., 2023) could be addressed by investing in volunteer management, providing training and support to retain staff, and raising awareness about food waste reduction and redistribution.

To address the **operational** risks in food sharing, particularly in handling, storing, and distributing food (Booth and Whelan, 2014), FSIs can provide comprehensive training for volunteers and staff in proper food handling and safety procedures. FSIs can invest in high-quality storage facilities or equip temporary facilities with optimal temperature and humidity controls to ensure the freshness and safety of food during storage. FSIs can improve their logistics plans to minimise travel time and equip vehicles with temperature control for transporting perishable food. This will require sufficient resources. To enhance operational resilience, FSIs can diversify food supply sources by partnering with a broader range of suppliers, including large retailers (e.g., supermarkets for near-expiry perishables), food processors (e.g., manufacturers donating surplus batches), local farms or auctions (e.g., for fresh produce), and community gardens (e.g., for seasonal fruits/vegetables). This approach reduces dependency on single sources, minimizes food waste, and improves supply consistency, as evidenced in structured systems like Belgium's food banks (De Boeck et al., 2017).

When **managing** FSIs, their operational scale should be adapted to match the limited capacity and time of participants (Berns et al., 2023). Providing clear guidelines for participation can facilitate effective contribution. Maintaining fair power distribution is crucial. This can be

achieved by avoiding the informal development of hierarchical leadership (Berns et al., 2023; Morrow, 2019b) and clear definition of roles and responsibilities. Effective communication and flexible decision-making are key to accommodating the complexities of fluctuating participation in FSIs. Participation in online platforms can be increased by making digital platforms user-friendly and providing digital literacy training.

Food safety and health risks have been identified as critical for the operation and image of food sharing organisations (Morrow, 2019b; Zurek, 2016). FSIs can undertake several measures to reduce these risks. By offering training for staff and volunteers on food handling, storage and safety, health risks can be minimised. They can also establish strict hygiene protocols for public fridges and other food sharing points to reduce the risk of food cross-contamination.

To ensure **justice** and **inclusivity** (Hennchen and Pregernig, 2020), FSIs can develop programmes that reach and serve underprivileged communities or people living in disadvantaged areas, ensuring that the benefits of food sharing are distributed equitably across different socio-economic groups. FSIs can collaborate with other actors, for example, education institutions and NGOs, to reduce the stigma associated with using food sharing (Makov et al., 2020) and instead create a positive image of it.

The risk of **rebound effects**, e.g. food sharing leading to the commodification of food (Michellini et al., 2018), can be mitigated through a balanced approach; thereby, platforms balance economic viability with their social mission of providing sustenance and welfare, integrating this approach into their design and operations. To avoid the rebound effects, it is important to educate the public, especially young people (Wiśniewska and Czernyszewicz, 2022), about responsible food consumption. Instilling in them the values of minimising food waste can have a profound impact on the environment. Understanding the value of food and the effort that goes into producing it fosters a sense of gratitude and respect for limited resources.

Transparency in FSIs' operations and motives can nurture public acceptance, **trust and image**. Respecting cultural sensitivity can reduce reluctance towards consuming surplus food (Makov et al., 2020). FSIs can work with platform designers to implement a robust user review and rating system to enhance trust in online food sharing platforms (Veen, 2019). FSIs can also develop simple checklists for food sharers who can provide information about the quality of food, its handling, storage conditions, and preparation methods. Addressing the structural and

systemic factors contributing to food waste, possibly through policy advocacy or collaborations, can further enhance the image and effectiveness of FSIs.

By building strong relationships with policy makers, industry leaders, the local community, and civil society, FSIs can strengthen their operations and financial viability. Their dependence on food donors (Berns et al., 2023) can be managed by diversifying food supply sources. FSIs should have mechanisms in place to resolve inter-organisational conflicts by encouraging open dialogue, negotiation, and compromise. Transparent and fair resource allocation and **network management processes** are crucial, especially when resources are scarce, and competition is fierce.

Our analysis revealed that several themes recur across the categories of challenges, risks and costs, creating strong interlinkages between them. For example, regulatory uncertainty not only constitutes a challenge to the establishment and scaling of FSIs but also generates risks related to liability and compliance and incurs additional legal costs. Similarly, trust and image feature as challenges in attracting users and building legitimacy, as risks in terms of transaction uncertainty and safety concerns, and as costs when resources must be invested in communication, insurance or monitoring systems. Social justice and inclusivity appear in multiple dimensions, both as a challenge for ensuring broad participation and as a risk when exclusion or stigma undermines the mission of FSIs. These overlaps highlight that the categories are not discrete but interdependent. By identifying cross-cutting themes, the review aimed to move beyond redundancy and instead show how common issues manifest in different ways across challenges, risks and costs. This approach also provided the foundation for our subsequent analysis of mitigation strategies and investment needs, which explicitly build on these correspondences to suggest more integrated ways forward.

The feasibility and long-term sustainability of the mitigation strategies identified in this review remain open questions, as these require empirical testing across different geographical, institutional, and organisational contexts; future research should therefore assess under what conditions these strategies can be successfully implemented and scaled.

4.2. Investment needs for FSIs

In section 3.3, we identified and analysed seven categories of costs that FSIs encounter during their operations and in their ambitions to appeal to the users and other key actors, such as governmental authorities or philanthropy organisations (Loh and Agyeman, 2019), on which their functioning may depend. These include costs related to the operations, administration, assets, personnel, communication and outreach, public relations and image, and legal compliance of FSIs (Fig. 5). The cost categories in the framework may overlap to some extent, but separating certain costs into stand-alone categories was necessary to emphasise them and highlight their importance for FSIs.

Our analysis shows that to establish and maintain FSIs and mitigate challenges and risks (section 4.1), investments are needed not only in financial terms but also in terms of human resources, space, equipment, and software. In Table 3, we connect investment needs with the cost categories from section 3.3 and identify specific products or processes in which FSIs need to invest.

A need for financial investments and investment in human resources cuts across nearly all cost categories. As such, FSIs need **money** (Yamabe-Ledoux et al., 2023) to purchase food from manufacturers, transport and store food, and pay their utility bills and rent or find a sponsor (Marovelli, 2019), e.g., a city council, a charity or other partner, who would cover these costs. FSIs also need money to purchase office supplies and hardware, software and subscriptions, certify their premises and purchase or rent vehicles, kitchenware and other equipment (Hennchen and Pregernig, 2020; Morrow, 2019b). Money is required to pay salaries to employees (Morrow, 2019b), for personnel training and

Table 3
Costs and investments for establishing, maintaining and scaling FSIs.

INVESTMENT NEEDS	COST CATEGORIES	INVESTMENT CATEGORIES
Finance	Operations	Food
	Administration	Utilities, rent, office supplies, subscriptions
	Assets	Hard- and software, equipment, premises certification
	Personnel	Salaries, training
	Public relations and image	Insurance
Human resources	Legal compliance	Licenses, certification, uniform for personnel, taxes, legal representation
	Operations	Time, knowledge, skills
	Administration	
	Personnel	
	Communication and outreach	
Space	Public relations and image	
	Legal compliance	
	Operations	Food storage space
Equipment	Administration	Operational premises (buildings, plots)
	Operations	Vehicles
	Assets	Hardware (computers, mobile phones), kitchenware and kitchen equipment, gardening equipment (landscaping tools)
Software	Assets	Mobile phone apps, websites, programmes

certification (Marovelli, 2019), as well as taxes, and cover insurance and legal representation costs. While direct costs for communication and outreach activities by FSIs were not articulated in the literature, to remain visible and appeal to their users and other key actors, FSIs may need to invest in communication materials and campaigns (Morrow, 2019b).

Investing in **human resources** in the form of time, knowledge, and skills of key people engaged in FSIs appears to be equally important to monetary investments, particularly since many FSIs rely entirely on volunteer labour (Berns et al., 2023). Employees and volunteers manage the daily operations of FSIs, do the paperwork, and build and maintain online and offline infrastructure (Morrow, 2019b), communities and FSI image, e.g., by monitoring and addressing online reviews and ensuring trustworthy and reliable face-to-face interactions with users. FSI volunteers or employees manage regular communication channels (e.g., a hotline, a newsletter, social media pages), engage in lobbying and legal representation of FSI interests, interact with city agencies, and keep the relevant documentation. FSIs need skilled and knowledgeable staff when it comes to food safety as well as when engaging in legal paperwork, e.g., signing liability agreements (Morrow, 2019b). Regarding assets, the literature has not provided a direct connection to the need for human resources. However, it is deemed essential for FSIs to have skilled personnel who can use the equipment to grow, prepare, store and redistribute food, as well as digitally literate staff able to work with phone apps, websites and platforms or find and install the necessary software.

Other investment needs of FSIs include those in infrastructure, namely space, equipment and software (Marovelli, 2019; Morrow, 2019b). FSIs need to invest in **space** for their operations as well as space for food storage. They also need various **equipment** to grow, transport, store, prepare and redistribute food. These include gardening equipment (e.g., landscaping tools), vehicles (e.g., trucks, cars, cargo bikes) and kitchen equipment (e.g., kitchenware, fridges, dishwashers, ovens, microwaves). FSIs also need hardware equipment (e.g., computers, mobile phones) and software (e.g., access to mobile phone apps, computer programmes, and websites) to support their daily operations.

4.3. The role of different stakeholders in facilitating food sharing

Our analysis indicates that the actors who feature in discussions about challenges and risks are frequently those who can also contribute to addressing these issues. While exploring strategies to address the identified challenges, mitigate the risks and considering investments to offset the costs, we found that the scope of inquiry expanded beyond FSIs to include other actors. This expansion is necessitated by the fact that FSIs function across diverse local, national, and sometimes international contexts, each with distinct institutional, cultural, and infrastructural settings. Hence, understanding how to navigate and leverage the roles of these varied actors is essential for developing a nuanced understanding of the investments required for establishing, maintaining, and scaling FSIs.

For example, **health authorities** are essential in addressing health and safety concerns. Local health authorities could collaborate with FSIs and provide guidance and oversight, ensuring alignment with public health standards. Health authorities can also conduct audits of food-sharing premises to ensure compliance with food safety standards and regulations.

Justice and inclusivity are important criteria for a well-functioning and appreciated FSI. While FSIs can work on improving their profile, municipalities have an essential role to play. **Municipalities** can offer digital literacy programmes for people lacking digital skills, enhancing their ability to participate in online food sharing.

Rebound effects associated with food sharing often depend on actors other than FSIs. Therefore, these actors can play a crucial role in developing conditions that reduce the risk and size of rebound effects. For example, **national and local governments** can work to address systemic issues leading to food poverty to avoid the risk of entrenching poverty through food sharing. **Retailer** voluntary programmes aimed at reducing food waste can ensure that the volume of near-expiry food is minimised as much as possible by retailers themselves. This can help reduce the rebound effect among retailers, who might feel less inclined to reduce their food waste when they know that FSIs will use the discarded food. Of course, since not all near-expiry food waste can be prevented through retailer programmes for various reasons, FSIs may step in to handle the remaining unavoidable food waste, ensuring it is redistributed rather than discarded.

The role of **educational institutions** in fostering responsible food consumption through sharing and preventing food waste is crucial for educating public. These institutions can integrate relevant topics into their curriculum, demonstrate waste reduction strategies in their operations, engage students in practical initiatives, collaborate with local communities and organisations, and contribute through research and innovation. By doing so, they impart sustainable habits and values that can be carried into adulthood, thereby shaping a more sustainable future.

Finally, addressing the regulatory uncertainty and risks in food sharing requires collaboration among different actors besides the compliance efforts of FSIs. Thus, **national policymakers** can alleviate the regulatory uncertainties confronting FSIs. This can be achieved by updating and tailoring current regulations to align more closely with the unique aspects and business models of FSIs. For example, it is essential to apply the precautionary principle judiciously to foster innovation and safeguard public health and safety. National policymakers can also craft new laws and guidelines for food sharing. **International policymakers** may need to establish legal frameworks that transcend national boundaries, which is especially important for FSIs with international operations. This will ensure uniformity and clarity in legal standards, facilitating the smoother operation of FSIs across different countries.

These are just a few examples of the role of other actors than FSIs identified in this literature review. However, previous studies have charted a broader array of stakeholders. For instance, actors upstream and downstream of the supply chain and community groups without direct engagement with FSIs have been acknowledged (Mackenzie and

Davies, 2019). Further research is needed to explore what role other actors in the food sharing landscape can play in addressing the challenges and risks and providing investments.

5. Conclusions

In addressing the urgent need for fundamental changes in our current food systems, this study explored the transformative potential of urban FSIs. The prevailing food systems are riddled with inefficiencies, leading to significant sustainability impacts. Alternative systems, such as food sharing, have emerged but face considerable challenges. Despite the growing research, recognition and appreciation of the value of FSIs, a comprehensive understanding of their operations remains fragmented and unsystematic. This article sought to provide a systematic understanding of the challenges, risks and costs of establishing and maintaining FSIs in urban contexts.

A systematic literature review of 55 academic articles was conducted. The findings are categorised into three primary levels: challenges, risks, and costs, each with a subset of second-level and third-level categories. The challenges are subdivided into six categories: organisational management, resources, user participation, network management, image, and regulations. Risks are also classified into six categories: health and safety, justice and inclusivity, rebound effects, operational risks, trust, and regulatory uncertainty. The costs encountered by FSIs are divided into seven categories: operational costs, administrative costs, assets, personnel costs, communication and outreach costs, public relations and image, and legal compliance costs. In addition, based on a comparative analysis of challenges, risks and costs, this study developed a set of mitigation strategies that FSIs can employ to address challenges and risks, as well as the investments – financial, human resources, space, equipment and software - required to establish, maintain, and scale FSIs. Furthermore, the study discusses the importance of actors other than FSIs in addressing some of the identified challenges, risks, and costs.

Given the high potential for the social impact of bottom-up local initiatives, this study stresses the need to develop pathways to scale FSIs. A deeper and more systematic understanding of the multi-dimensional challenges, risks, and costs faced by FSIs can be instrumental for organisations, citizens, and policymakers to formulate goals, acquire skills, and gather resources needed to grow and scale food sharing in cities. The key findings benefit urban FSIs interested in developing their practice, building capacity, and contributing to resilient and sustainable urban food systems. On a broader scale, sustainability benefits of developed urban FSIs align with SDGs on alleviating hunger and creating resilient cities and communities.

Although this study is based on a systematic and comprehensive literature review, it does have some limitations. For example, it was impossible to differentiate which costs and investments would be more profound during specific lifecycle phases of FSIs, i.e. in their design and start-up phase, during their operation and maintenance, and in their potential scaling up phase. Collecting and analysing empirical data with a more nuanced breakdown of costs and investments in different development phases could be important for FSIs. While the review highlights a broad range of challenges, risks, and costs across different types of FSIs, it is important to note that the available literature does not provide sufficiently representative or comparable data to generalise systematically across the initiative with different organizational forms (e.g., for-profit versus non-profit, digital platforms versus community-based initiatives) or explore which factors (e.g. type of users, FSI goals) matter as factors for differences in challenges, risks and costs. Such differentiation is an important future research step which would allow for a more precise assessment of the mitigation strategies and investment needs required for scaling under diverse conditions.

From a practical standpoint, the categorisation of risks, challenges and costs facilitates a more nuanced understanding of the factors that FSIs should consider when establishing an initiative or planning its

scalability. The systematic vision of risks and challenges enables FSIs to conduct a comprehensive analysis of the external environment and to evaluate their internal resources. The categorisation of costs provides a comprehensive overview of the significant expenditure incurred by FSIs during their operations. The proposed mitigation strategies and investment needs offer actionable guidance for FSIs to secure resources and build partnerships, fostering resilience and scalability. It is also possible that other important stakeholders, such as municipalities and policymakers, may find the findings useful in better directing their support to FSIs and in creating favourable policies that would serve to reduce existing risks and challenges.

For the future research directions, empirically based analysis of challenges, risks, costs, and related investments would be essential for various FSIs, such as those involved in growing, cooking and eating food together, and redistributing of surplus food. The articles in this analysis have mainly focused on surplus food redistribution (48 articles out of 55), and food growing was studied in just eight articles. Costs and investments will likely be different for various types of FSIs. The geographical distribution of the reviewed articles underscores a predominance of European and Western contexts in the literature, with opportunities for future research to expand empirical insights from underrepresented regions, such as Africa and Asia, to better capture the contextual nuances of FSIs worldwide. Recognition of different cultural and geographical contexts should receive greater attention as FSIs operate in diverse regulatory and cultural environments, which significantly influence their scalability and acceptance. This emphasises the need to empirically test, enrich and tailor the proposed frameworks on challenges, risks, and costs for the four FSI types, including those that 1) facilitate cooking and eating together, 2) growing or composting together, 3) redistributing surplus food, and 4) sharing food space, tools, knowledge, and seeds. Furthermore, the domain of food sharing is characterised by the prevalence of qualitative analysis of initiatives, with a scarcity of numerical data, including metrics such as weight and scope of costs in relation to the specific type of FSIs.

Importantly, this research identified other critical for FSIs actors with power and resources. These include but are not limited to governments and policymakers, health authorities, retailers, and charity organisations. Further research is needed to map a full array of influential actors in the food sharing landscape and explore the roles they can play in addressing the challenges and risks and providing investments to FSIs.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Vera Sadovska: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Yuliya Voytenko Palgan:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Oksana Mont:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used Grammarly, Copilot and DeepL services in the writing process to improve readability and language. After using these services, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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